

Integrated Urban Wastewater Management in Greater Copenhagen and its digital future

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Abstract: Increasing pressure on Greater Copenhagen's utilities due to environmental requirements, climate change, a growing city and economic regulations, makes the use of advanced digital solutions in Integrated Urban Wastewater Management crucial. Motivated by complying with the EU Water Framework Directive (EU 2000) for 'Øresund' to reduce nitrogen emissions as well as to optimize the sewer system across their many shareholders, BIOFOS joined a large Intereuropean Research and Demonstration project, Digital Water City (DWC), under the Horizon2020 program. The main aim is to produce reliable inflow forecasts using machine learning for decision support in operations. Development and adaptation of three digital solutions, including machine learning inflow forecasts, has been executed during the last two years, and the technology is now being tested.

Keywords: Machine Learning; Integrated Wastewater Management; Decision Support

Introduction

'Øresund' is the receiving water body for two of the three wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) operated by BIOFOS, the largest WWTP utility in Denmark. To comply with the EU Water Framework Directive (EU 2000) in Denmark, in 2027 for 'Øresund' the annual emissions of nitrogen (N) must be reduced by 240 tons. To achieve this, it is essential to reduce bypass water (mechanically treated wastewater) since it contains a large amount of nitrogen. Besides sharper environmental and economic regulations, a growing city, and need for climate change adaptation put pressure on Greater Copenhagen's utilities to innovate to optimize the sewer system across their many shareholders. The WWTPs receive wastewater from seven different utilities with individually operated collections systems. The complexity in managing the entire system calls for integrated digital solutions, including data collection and sharing. Within the Horizon2020 project Digital Water Cities, development and adaptation of three digital solutions has been executed during the last two years, which are now being tested. The digital solutions are "Improved machine learning (ML) sewer inflow forecast", "Decision Support System for real-time control of WWTP operations and in-sewer retention", and "Web-based prototype platform for decision support at city scale"

The paper presents the methods applied in the DWC project and the results obtained.

METHODS

Digital solution 1 - Improved machine learning (ML) sewer inflow forecast

The treatment plant operators apply different operational strategies during dry and wet weather. Since transitioning between strategies takes 1-2 hours, advance information on when flow rates exceed the threshold for switching strategy is valuable. The treatment plant currently uses a relatively simple forecast. A key component in the

current project was developing a faster, more accurate and robust forecast. The ML model produces a 3-hour forecast of the inflow to the WWTP. As input, the machine learning model takes rain intensity categories at selected locations as well as level, flow, and volume observations in the system. The rain categories are derived from weather radar data preprocessed by a deep learning model. Different ML models were evaluated, and gradient boosting from LightGBM (Guolin Ke, 2017) performed best and trained fastest.

Digital solution 2 - DSS for real-time control of WWTP operations and in-sewer retention

This solution includes a calibrated hydrodynamic (HIFI) model of the catchment. The model is driven by real-time sensor data, including a 3-hour radar forecast. Like the ML model, the HIFI model produces a 3-hour inflow forecast, and the WWTP operators can compare results of control strategies. The goal is to optimize the integrated control between in-sewer storage in the catchment and WWTP.

Digital solution 3 - Web-based platform for decision support at city scale

The platform provides a full overview of key data and processes in the catchment and includes both, a GIS-like overview with selected timeseries, and a dashboard with key data e.g., on rainfall predictions. The solution fosters stakeholder engagement and rational decision making based on real-time data, accurate modelling and scenario analyses. An important validation of the project value has been to produce documentation of the performance and reliability of the digital solutions using Key Performance Indicators, like saved annual emissions or RMSE errors between forecasted and measured flow.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Figure 1.1 shows an example of ML results. In Highlight 1, the ML model overpredicted while the current model underpredicted. Rain was predicted for several locations (middle plot), while little to no rain was observed (top plot), explaining the ML overprediction. In highlight 2, no rain was observed, and both models underpredicted. The higher observed flow could be due to storage basin emptying. In highlight 3, the ML model predicted the magnitude of flow more accurately and the current model pinpointed the time of increased flow better.

Figure 1.2 shows an example from the web presentation tool – digital solution 3, displaying the different forecast from the machine learning and HIFI models.

Flow predictions made at lead time 60

Figure 1.1 Comparison of forecasted and observed rain and the impact on the forecasted flows.

Figure 1.2 Screen capture from the web interface, showing forecasted flows.

CONCLUSIONS

The digital solutions described above have been installed and deployed in Q3 2021. The system will be further evaluated until Q2 2022. The first results confirm the assumption that use of ML forecasts improve accuracy of the inflow forecast. Easy access to sensor data and predictions via the web- platform will improve system understanding and can be used by the operators to optimize control of the WWTP.

REFERENCES

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